

More prime counters

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All odd primes are of the form $p = \pm 1 + 4k$ for some integer $k \geq 1$ **[1]**, but not conversely.

To get some of these, execute first the following MATLAB/OCTAVE scripts:

```
for k=1:2.5e6,p1(k)=isprime(1+4*k);,end  
for k=1:2.5e6,p2(k)=isprime(-1+4*k);,end
```

Thus p_1 and p_2 are indicator functions of these disjoint sets; the commands

```
sum(p1);,sum(p2)
```

give the total prime count for each set: 332,180 and 332,398 respectively; the sum of which yields exactly the total number of odd primes up to 10 million (664,579), as expected.

Next, the commands

```
for k=1:2.5e6,int1(k)=1+4*k;end  
for k=1:2.5e6,int2(k)=-1+4*k;end
```

generate the respective integers; to now extract only the primes, do

```
pr1=nonzeros(p1.*int1);  
pr2=nonzeros(p2.*int2);
```

The first twelve such primes are, respectively

5 13 17 29 37 41 53 61 73 89 97 101

and

3 7 11 19 23 31 43 47 59 67 71 79

The indicators

```
n1=1-p1;, n2=1-p2;
```

will yield the count for the remaining odd integers; do

```
sum(n1);,sum(n2)
```

to get 2,167,820 and 2,167,602; the grand sum of all odd integers is 5 million, as expected.

Now, to extract the remaining odds (od_1 and od_2) do

```
od1=nonzeros(n1.*int1);  
od2=nonzeros(n2.*int2);
```

The first twelve are

9 21 25 33 45 49 57 65 69 77 81 85

(squares are underlined) and

15 27 35 39 51 55 63 75 87 91 95 99

Only the set {od1} has squares; as a way to get these, first get their indicator function:

$q1=1+\text{sign}(\text{floor}(\text{sqrt}(\text{od1}))- \text{sqrt}(\text{od1}));$

and then the command

$\text{sum}(q1)$

gives the squares count as 1,580. Furthermore, the command

$\text{sum}(\text{isprime}(\text{sqrt}(q1.*\text{od1})))$

gives the count of odd-prime-squares up to 10 million: 445; 3,137 is the last such prime.

500 computations every 20,000 integers up to 10 million showed there were more primes of the p2 variety. The image below plots the counts difference (top tier), showing jagged, fractal behavior; its 32-bin histogram in the lower tier is decidedly not gaussian. Kurtosis is 2.121.

Finally, what about the counters here?

The computations yielded the estimates

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_1(n) &= \#\{\text{primes of the form } p_1 = 1 + 4k, k \leq n\} \\ &\approx n/(\log_{10}(n) + (177/145)) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_2(n) &= \#\{\text{primes of the form } p_2 = -1 + 4k, k \leq n\} \\ &\approx n/(\log_{10}(n) + (106/87)) \end{aligned}$$

for sufficiently large n , beyond (say) 9 million.

Percent errors for these estimated counters are shown below; in blue for π_1 , orange for π_2 .

Zoomed-in tail ends are displayed next, from when errors were below .1% (beyond 9 million.)

Reference. Dieudonné, 'Mathematics – The Music of Reason', Springer, 1998, Appendix IV.